

Voltammetric simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt in industrial waste waters

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Abstract : A convenient and precise method was developed for simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt using differential pulse polarography (DPP). Limit of determination of 0.009 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.04 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were achieved for nickel and cobalt, respectively. Major metal ions such as ferric iron, copper, lead and zinc did not interfere.

Keywords : Nickel, cobalt, DPP, industrial waste waters.

Introduction

It is somewhat difficult to make sequential determination of two and more species when present together in environmental samples by commonly employed techniques such as spectrophotometry, spectrofluorimetry, atomic absorption and ion selective electrodes. Voltammetric methods such as anodic stripping voltammetry and differential pulse polarography (DPP) have proved useful in such determinations due to the selectivity of the redox potential^{1,2}. Our aim of this study was to develop a suitable method of simple approach for the simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt using voltammetric methods. The voltammetric determination of nitrate-nitrite³, and bromide-chloride⁴ has been reported earlier. Nickel and cobalt have definite industrial and toxicological importance. Nickel is used in alloys, especially stainless steel, metal plating and catalysis. Many of Ni compounds likewise nickel carbonyls are extremely toxic. Cobalt compounds generally have low toxicity⁵. Co^{60} is a useful radioisotope.

Voltammetric data on nickel and cobalt reveals that many authors have reported the voltammetric determination of nickel and cobalt with complexing

ligands such as dimethylglyoxime^{6,7}, thiocarbomates⁸, furildioxime⁹ and nioxime¹⁰. Adeloju and Briggs¹¹ have shown differential pulse adsorptive voltammetric determination of nickel and cobalt in biological materials. Morfobus *et al.*¹² have determined Ni^{II} and Co^{II} by square wave adsorptive voltammetry at a rotating disc bismuth electrode. Safavi and Shams¹³, and Legeai *et al.*¹⁴ have shown adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry for trace analysis of nickel and cobalt. Kapturski and Bobrowski¹⁵ have reported the adsorptive stripping voltammetric determination of nickel and cobalt. Segura *et al.*¹⁶ have studied the adsorptive stripping voltammetry of nickel at bismuth film electrode. Cyclic voltammetric study of nickel was reported by Skljarevski *et al.*¹⁷.

Previously we have used furildioxime in determination of nickel and cobalt¹⁸. It was observed that in presence of complexing media peak potential of metal ions shifted significantly and it makes inconvenient for interference studies. In this way interference of cadmium and lead could be determined. Herein, by employing a simple non-complexing ammonical medium (ammonium chloride-ammonium acetate), it was possible to monitor the presence of commonly occurring metal ions in industrial waste waters such as copper, zinc and iron for their interference. In addition determination limit of Ni and Co were lowered down to 0.09 µg/ml and 0.04 µg/ml, respectively from 0.04 µg/ml and 0.15 µg/ml achieved in previous work. In keeping view of these advantageous the present study was carried out.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

(i) Voltammetric set-up :

A microprocessor based pulse polarographic analyzer (Model CL-362) in combination with a drop-timer assembly, all of Elico Ltd., Hyderabad, India was used for voltammetric measurements. Voltammograms were recorded by an Epson printer (Epson-LX-300+II). Potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and a platinum wire acted as an auxiliary electrode throughout. The instrumental settings are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Instrumental conditions of DPP

Pulse amplitude	50 mV
Pulse duration	57 ms
Clock time of pulse	1 s
Scan rate	12 mV/s

(ii) AAS :

An atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Model AA-2380), of Perkin-Elmer, USA was also used for sample analysis. It has wavelength range of 1900–9000 Å with selectable slit width and Czerny-turner grating monochromator. The hollow cathode lamp of the concerned metal (nickel and cobalt) was fitted with selective wavelength. The flow rate of air-acetylene flame gas was adjusted. These conditions were maintained for 20 min to stabilize and to obtain the maximum sensitivity of equipment. The standard solution of metals was aspirated into the flame and absorption was noted at 232 nm and 241 nm for Ni and Co, respectively. This procedure was followed for industrial waste water samples and concentrations were determined by calibration curve method.

(iii) pH meter :

The pH measurements were made by a digital pH meter (Model-5000) of Lab India.

Sample preparation :

(i) Standard samples :

The Millipore Quality Assurance System (Model-A 643) was employed to obtain Milli-Q water of analytical grade. Standard samples were prepared using Milli-Q water. Stock solution of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} were prepared from nickel nitrate and cobalt nitrate, respectively. Chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Sample collection and preservation :

Industrial waste water samples were collected in clean polyethylene containers from different metal industries located in Basni Industrial Area of Jodhpur. Containers were kept filled with 0.1 M hydrochloric acid until the time of sample collection. Samples were filtered through Whatman filter paper no. 42 and acidified with HCl to pH ~ 2 for storage¹⁹.

Sample treatment :

A 100 ml aliquot of sample was treated with 1 ml of an oxidizing mixture of nitric acid and sulfuric acid to destroy the biological and organic matters²⁰.

Results and discussion*Polarographic characteristics and choice of medium :*

In preliminary investigations different supporting electrolytes such as potassium chloride, sodium chloride-sodium acetate, lithium chloride-ammonium acetate were studied to observe the electroreduction of nickel and cobalt at dropping mercury electrode. 0.1 M ammonium chloride in 0.1 M ammonium acetate was found to be the most adequate medium where well-defined polarographic waves representing Ni^{II}-Ni⁰ and Co^{II}-Co⁰ were obtained at -1.0 V and -1.29 V, respectively. The results are shown in Table 2. The direct current polarographic observations revealed that the electrode process of nickel and cobalt was not fully reversible, however waves appeared to be diffusion controlled.

Table 2. Polarographic characteristics of nickel(II) and cobalt(II)

$$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M, \text{Co}^{\text{II}} = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$$

Sr. no.	Supporting electrolyte	Ni ^{II}		Co ^{II}	
		$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (μA)
1.	0.1 M NH ₄ Cl	0.93	0.40	1.31	0.50
2.	0.2 M H ₃ PO ₄	1.09	0.62	1.28	0.35
3.	0.1 M NaCl	1.10	0.30	1.28	0.36
4.	0.1 M NH ₄ Cl in 0.1 M NH ₄ OAc	1.00	2.15	1.29	1.34

DPP studies :

The optimal conditions for simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt were found by carrying out detailed DPP studies. Ni^{II} and Co^{II} also showed differential pulse peaks and peak current increased linearly upto 32 ppm (Fig. 1). The characteristics of calibration curves are given in Table 3.

Interference :

The coexisting metal ions with nickel and cobalt in industrial waste waters such as copper and ferric iron were tested for their interference

Fig. 1. The calibration plot (conc. vs peak current) of nickel and cobalt in 0.1 M NH₄Cl in 0.1 M NH₄OAc.

Table 3. Calibration characteristics of Ni^{II} and Co^{II}

Parameters	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}
Slope	0.101	0.077
Coefficient of correlation (<i>r</i>)	0.998	0.999
Intercept	0.081	-0.009
Standard deviation (±)	1.124	0.843

during the simultaneous determination of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} by DPP. The potential of Fe^{II} in ammonium chloride-ammonium acetate medium was noticed at more positive potential (> 0.0 V), thus did not interfere. Similarly, Cu^{II} gave a DP peak at -0.26 V. Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} which are generally present in industrial waste waters also showed distinguishable DP peaks (Fig. 2). Peak potentials are listed in Table 4.

Recovery studies :

DPP measurements were evaluated for precision and accuracy to ensure the quality of method. The results were found quantitative in terms of average recovery (< 98%). Relevant data are presented in Table 5.

Fig. 2. DP polarogram of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) in presence of copper, lead, cadmium and zinc, in 0.1 M NH₄Cl in 0.1 M NH₄OAc : Cu^{II}, 1 ppm; Pb^{II}, 12 ppm; Cd^{II}, 4 ppm; Zn^{II}, 2 ppm; Ni^{II}, 3 ppm; Co^{II}, 5 ppm.

Table 4. Peak potential of metal ions in 0.1 M NH₄Cl in 0.1 M NH₄OAc

Metal ions	$-E_p$ (V) vs SCE
Ferric iron(III)	>0.00
Copper(II)	0.23
Lead(II)	0.43
Cadmium(II)	0.68
Nickel(II)	1.00
Zinc(II)	1.13
Cobalt(II)	1.29

Table 5. Recovery studies on determination of nickel and cobalt

Metal ion	Conc. (µg/ml)		Recovery (%)
	Present	Determined ^a	
Ni ^{II}	2.0	1.95	97.5
Co ^{II}	2.0	1.96	98.0
Average	97.7		

^aN=5, number of determinations.

Limit of determination :

The limit of determination of nickel and cobalt in optimal experimental conditions was found to be 0.09 µg/ml and 0.15 µg/ml, respectively.

Analytical applications :

DPP method was applied to determine nickel and cobalt in industrial waste water samples.

Voltammetric measurements :

The pretreated sample was taken into the polarographic cell with 0.1 M ammonium chloride-ammonium acetate. Polarograms were recorded from -0.0 V to -1.6 V. Peak currents were measured at -1.0 V and -1.29 V, after making the blank correction for nickel(II) and cobalt(II), respectively. Concentrations were quantified by standard addition method²¹. The results so obtained are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Results of DPP determination of nickel and cobalt in samples of industrial waste waters

Sr. no.	Sample	Conc. (ppm) ^a ± SD	
		Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺
1.	Common Nala ^b	0.701 ± 0.006	0.028 ± 0.002
2.	Jodhpur Metal Works	0.180 ± 0.003	0.024 ± 0.004
3.	Laxmi Industries	0.314 ± 0.004	0.018 ± 0.006
4.	Marudhar Industries	0.216 ± 0.005	0.015 ± 0.003

^aLocated in Basni Industrial Area.

^bAverage of three determinations.

Initial concentration of other metal ions (Common Nala) : Cu^{II}, 0.25 ppm; Pb^{II}, 0.08 ppm; Cd^{II}, 0.002 ppm; Zn^{II}, 0.037 ppm.

Comparison :

Standard samples in lieu of SRM were prepared in laboratory by adding known concentration of nickel and cobalt. These samples were analyzed by DPP and AAS method to demonstrate the validity of method. The results of DPP determination of nickel and cobalt in different samples of industrial waste were further verified by carrying out comparison studies with AAS method. The comparative data are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Comparative results of determination of nickel and cobalt by DPP and AAS methods

Sr. no.	Conc. present (ppm)	Conc. found (ppm)			
		Nickel(II)		Cobalt(II)	
		DPP	AAS	DPP	AAS
1.	Real sample ^a	0.701	0.728	0.028	0.029
2.	1	1.706	1.736	1.028	1.031
3.	2	2.698	2.732	2.030	2.034
4.	3	3.703	3.729	3.030	3.032
5.	4	4.709	4.738	4.032	4.036
6.	5	5.718	5.740	5.035	5.038

^aCommon Nala industrial waste water sample.
N = number of determinations = 3.

Conclusion

The observations have enabled the development of a convenient differential pulse polarographic method for simultaneous determination of nickel and cobalt with better limit of determination and accuracy. The method will be useful in research and industrial laboratories where nickel and cobalt are used in alloys to improve mechanibility, especially in stainless steel.

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References

1. H. W. Nurnberg, "Approved Voltammetric Methods for the Determination of Some Toxic Trace Metals", Nuclear Research Centre Publication, K.F.A., Juelich, 1977.
2. P. T. Kissinger and W. R. Heineman, "Laboratory Techniques in Electroanalytical Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1984.
3. P. Sharma and R. Sharma, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 2002, **82**, 7.
4. P. Sharma and R. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2048.
5. J. Emsley, "The Elements", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1988.
6. C. J. Flora and E. Nieboer, *Anal. Chem.*, 1980, **52**, 1013.

7. B. Pihlar, P. Valenta and H. W. Nurnberg, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1981, **307**, 337.
8. H. T. Delves, G. S. Shepherd and P. Vinter, *Analyst*, 1977, **96**, 260.
9. D. Mikac-Devic, S. Nomoto and F. W. Sunderman, *Clin. Chem.*, 1977, **23**, 948.
10. M. Korolczuk, A. Moroziewicz, M. Grabarczyk and K. Paluszek, *Talanta*, 2005, **65**, 1003.
11. S. B. Adeloju and T. Tran, *Anal. Lett.*, 1986, **19**, 1633.
12. M. Morfobus, A. Economou and A. Voulgaropoulos, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **519**, 57.
13. A. Safavi and E. Shams, *Talanta*, 200, **51**, 1117.
14. S. Legeai, S. Bois and O. Vittori, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2006, **591**, 93.
15. P. Kapturski and A. Bobrowski, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2008, **617**, 1.
16. R. Segura, M. Pradena, D. Pinto, F. Godoy, E. Nagles and V. Arancibia, *Talanta*, 2011, **85**, 2316.
17. S. Skljarevski, A. P. Angela and D. G. Peters, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2011, **661**, 39.
18. P. Sharma, S. Kumbhat and C. Rawat, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1992, **48**, 201.
19. T. S. West and H.W. Nurnberg, "The Determination of Trace Metals in Natural Waters", Blackwell Scientific Publishers, Oxford, 1988.
20. A. E. Greenberg, J. J. Connors and D. Jenkins (eds.), "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water", 15th ed., American Public Health Association, New York, 1981.
21. H. Willard, L. Merit and J. Dean, "Instrumental Methods of Analysis", 5th ed., D. Van Nostrand, New York, 1974.